

Blood Iron Status of Menorrhagic Female Students of Babcock University, Ogun State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Background: Menorrhagia, or heavy menstrual bleeding, can lead to significant blood iron depletion, affecting overall health. This study assesses the blood iron status of menorrhagic female students at Babcock University, Ogun State, Nigeria.

Objective: To evaluate the serum iron levels, total iron-binding capacity (TIBC), and related haematological parameters in menorrhagic female students and compare them with non-menorrhagic counterparts.

Materials and Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted between February and May 2019 at Babcock University. Seventy-one female students, aged 18-25, were recruited. A total of 38 menorrhagic and 33 non-menorrhagic females served as test and control groups, respectively. Blood samples were collected for the determination of serum iron, TIBC, and haematological indices. Serum iron and TIBC were measured using the Biosystems test kits, and hepcidin levels were quantified via ELISA. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23, with independent t-tests and correlation analyses performed.

Results: Menorrhagic females had a significantly higher mean TIBC (518.50 ± 146.92 µg/dl) compared to controls (443.08 ± 144.34 µg/dl, $p=0.033$). No significant differences were observed in other parameters such as mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH), and white blood cell count (WBC) between the groups.

Conclusion: Menorrhagic female students at Babcock University demonstrated altered iron metabolism, particularly in elevated TIBC levels, suggesting the need for targeted interventions to manage potential iron deficiencies.

Keywords: Menorrhagia, Serum Iron, TIBC, Haematological Indices, Hepcidin, Female Students

INTRODUCTION

Iron deficiency remains a major public health concern, particularly among women of reproductive age, due to menstruation-related blood loss. Menorrhagia, defined as excessive menstrual bleeding, can lead to significant iron depletion and ultimately iron deficiency anemia (IDA) if not managed properly. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that over 30% of the global population is affected by anemia, with iron deficiency accounting for nearly half of these cases.^[1] Among young females, especially students, iron deficiency poses additional challenges, including cognitive impairment, reduced physical performance, and diminished academic achievement.^[2]

Babcock University, located in Ogun State, Nigeria, is home to a diverse population of female students, many of whom may suffer from menorrhagia without access to proper medical attention or nutritional interventions. The university setting presents an opportunity to explore how excessive menstrual bleeding affects iron status and overall health in this demographic. Studies have shown that the prevalence of iron deficiency anemia among young women in Nigeria is alarmingly high, often due to inadequate dietary intake of iron-rich foods, poor menstrual hygiene, and limited access to healthcare.^[3,4]

Menorrhagia contributes significantly to iron depletion as it leads to increased iron loss through chronic blood loss. Normally, the body loses small amounts of iron daily, which are typically replenished through diet. However, in cases of menorrhagia, the body may not compensate for the excessive iron loss, leading to a negative iron balance. This condition exacerbates the risk of developing iron deficiency, which, if left untreated, can evolve into iron deficiency anemia (IDA). IDA is particularly concerning because it affects the oxygen-carrying capacity of blood, leading to symptoms such as fatigue, weakness, dizziness, and in severe cases, cardiovascular complications.^[5]

Iron deficiency remains a public health issue in Nigeria despite efforts to improve nutrition through fortification programs. The socio-cultural practices surrounding menstruation may further compound the problem, as many young women do not seek medical advice for heavy periods, considering them normal. This cultural perception of menstrual health may delay diagnosis and treatment, putting young women at risk of chronic anemia and other related health issues.^[6]

Research on iron status among female students, particularly those experiencing menorrhagia, is critical for understanding the scope of the problem in university populations. Previous studies have indicated that the incidence of menorrhagia among adolescent girls ranges from 10% to 20%, with many cases going undiagnosed and untreated.^[7] Such data underscore the importance of routine screening for iron deficiency in female students, especially those reporting heavy menstrual bleeding.

Additionally, lifestyle factors such as diet, physical activity, and stress may further influence the iron status of students. In a university environment, where academic pressures are high, students may not prioritize balanced

diets, often resorting to convenient but nutrient-poor foods. ^[8] This dietary pattern, coupled with menorrhagia, can accelerate the depletion of iron stores, leading to iron deficiency. A study conducted by Ahmed et al. revealed that young women with menorrhagia were more likely to have suboptimal iron levels, which negatively impacted their quality of life. ^[9]

Babcock University provides a unique setting to explore these dynamics. As a private institution with a mix of students from diverse backgrounds, it presents an opportunity to assess how socio-economic factors, awareness, and access to healthcare influence the management of menorrhagia and iron deficiency. Furthermore, the study could offer insights into the effectiveness of existing university health programs in addressing the nutritional and health needs of female students with menorrhagia.

The findings from this research could inform policies aimed at improving menstrual health education, encouraging early diagnosis and treatment of menorrhagia, and promoting dietary interventions to prevent iron deficiency. Addressing the blood iron status of menorrhagic female students could have far-reaching implications for their academic performance, physical health, and overall well-being.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY AREA

The cross-sectional study was conducted at Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria, to assess the blood Iron status among menorrhagic female students of Babcock University, Ogun State, Nigeria between February and May 2019.

Sample Size Determination

The sample size was determined using the Cochran formula for estimating proportions in a population outlined by Uduma et al. ^[10]:

$$n = \frac{Z^2(Pq)}{e^2}$$

where n = minimum sample size

Z = 1.96 at 95% confidence level,

P = known/expected prevalence

e = error margin tolerated at 5% = 0.05

q = 1 - p

The existing prevalence is 4.8%.

P = 4.8% = 0.048

q = 1 - p

= 1 - 0.048

= 0.952

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2(0.048 \times 0.952)}{(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{3.8416 \times (0.045696)}{0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{0.1755}{0.0025} = 70.2$$

A total of 71 blood specimen samples were collected from consenting female students of Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun state.

ELIGIBILITY OF SUBJECTS

Inclusion Criteria

- Menorrhagic young females
- Female subjects within the age range of 18 and 25 years
- Females who have a heavy and longer menstrual flow of longer than 7 days.
- Healthy young females
- Females on Iron supplements or any other medication

Exclusion Criteria

- ✓ Unhealthy young females
- ✓ Female subjects below and above 18 and 25 years respectively.
- ✓ Subjects who are unwilling to provide consent for collection of data.

Consent

Informed consent was obtained from each participant. The purpose and nature of the study, as well as the method of the sample collection, were explained to them properly. Afterwards, participants were admitted into the study after signing an informed consent as proof of willingness to provide samples for the test. They were assured of the confidentiality associated with the study and the freedom to back out at any research stage.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Babcock University Health Research Ethics Committee (BUHREC) before the commencement of the study. The approval reference for the survey was BUHREC197/19.

Sample Collection

About 5ml of venous blood was obtained from each subject by a medical laboratory scientist in the haematology department via venepuncture. The samples were placed into their respective anticoagulation tubes, the EDTAK2 and the lithium heparin bottle, to prevent clotting of the blood samples, which were transported to the laboratory for processing.

LABORATORY ANALYSIS

Determination of Full Blood Count (FBC)

The tests were carried out by the automatic analyser following the manufacturer's instructions of the operation manual.

Determination of Iron and Total Iron Binding Capacity (TIBC)

The iron and TIBC tests were estimated using the Biosystems reagents and instruments test kit. The principles, procedures and precautions were observed and done according to the manufacturer's instructions.

The principle of the Iron test

Transferrin-bound ferric ions in the sample are released by guanidinium and reduced to ferrous utilizing ascorbic acid. Ferrous ion reacts with ferrozine forming a coloured complex that can be measured by spectrophotometry.

The principle of TIBC test

Excess of Ferric ion (Fe^{3+}) is added to the saturated serum transferrin. Uncomplexed ferric ion (Fe^{3+}) is precipitated with magnesium hydroxide carbonate and the iron bonded to protein in the supernatant is then spectrophotometrically measured.

Test Procedure for Serum Iron (Quantitative method of analysis)

The working reagent was prepared by transferring the content of one Reagent B vial containing Ferrozine and ascorbic acid into the Reagent A bottle that contained guanidinium chloride and an acetate buffer. And then was mixed thoroughly. Other volumes were prepared by adding 1ml of Reagent B and 4ml of Reagent A.

The following were then dispensed into labelled test tubes using an automatic pipette.

	Reagent Blank	Sample Blank	Sample	Standard
Distilled Water	200 μ l	-	-	-
Sample	-	200 μ l	200 μ l	-
Iron Standard	-	-	-	200 μ l
Reagent A	-	1.0ml	-	-
Working Reagent	1.0ml	-	1.0ml	1.0ml

- They were then mixed thoroughly and allowed to stand in the test tubes for 5 minutes at room temperature.
- Then the absorbance (A) of the Sample Blanks were read at 560nm against distilled water.
- Then the absorbance (A) of the Samples and the Standard were read against the reagent blank at 560nm.

Calculations

The iron concentration in the sample was calculated using the following general formula:

$$\text{Concentration of Sample} = \frac{A_{\text{sample}} - A_{\text{sample blank}} \times \text{Concentration of Standard}}{A_{\text{standard}}}$$

Where:

A_{Sample} = Absorbance of Sample

$A_{\text{Sample Blank}}$ = Absorbance of Sample Blank

A_{Standard} = Absorbance of Standard

Concentration of Standard = 200 µg/dL

Reference Range: For serum iron in females is between 50 – 170µg/dl. Different laboratories often use different units and “normal” may vary by population and the laboratory technique used.

Test Procedure for Total Iron Binding Capacity (Quantitative method of analysis)

The following were dispensed into labelled test tubes using an automatic pipette

Sample	0.5ml
Reagent (A)	1.0ml

They were then mixed thoroughly and allowed to stand for 5-30minutes at room temperature. To each tube one spoonful of Reagent (B) was added. It was then mixed thoroughly and allowed to stand for 30-60 minutes at room temperature. During this period, it was mixed thoroughly several times. It was then centrifuged at a minimum of 3000 revolution per minute for 10 minutes. Then the supernatant was carefully collected. Then the iron concentration in the supernatant was measured using the Iron BioSystems test kit.

Calculations

Total Iron Binding Capacity (TIBC) = Iron concentration in the supernatant X 3(dilution)

Reference Range

The reference range for serum TIBC in females is between 250-425µg/dl. Different laboratories often use different units and “normal” may vary by population and the laboratory technique used.

Hepcidin ELISA (Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay)

The Hepcidin concentration was estimated using the DRG Hepcidin ELISA test kit. The principles, procedures and precautions were observed and done according to the manufacturer’s instructions.

Principle of the test

The hepcidin ELISA kit is a solid phase that works based on the principle of competitive binding. Microtiter wells that are coated with a monoclonal antibody are directed towards the antigenic site of the bioactive hepcidin 25b molecule. The endogenous hepcidin of a patient serum sample is what competes with the added

hepcidin-biotin conjugate for binding to the coated antibody. After incubation, the unbound complex is then washed off. Then there is addition of substrate solution results in colour development which is stopped after a short period of incubation. The intensity of the colour obtained is reversely proportional to the concentration of hepcidin in the samples.

Test Procedure

About 10 μ l of sample buffer was added to each microtiter well. Then 20 μ l of each standard, control and samples was dispensed into the appropriate wells. Then it was incubated for 30 minutes at room temperature on a plate shaker at 500rpm. Then 150 μ l of assay buffer and 100 μ l of enzyme conjugate was added to each well. They were incubated for 180 minutes at room temperature on a plate shaker at 500rpm. The content was briskly shaken out of the well. After which the wells were rinsed 5 times with diluted wash solutions (400 μ l) per well. The wells were then stroked sharply on absorbent paper to remove residual droplets. Then 100 μ l of enzyme complex was dispensed into each well. It was incubated for 45 minutes at room temperature. After which the contents were briskly shaken out and the wells rinsed 5 times. 100 μ l of substrate solution was then added to each well. Then incubated for 30 minutes at room temperature. After which the enzymatic reaction was stopped by adding 100 μ l of stop solution to each well. Then the absorbance was then determined for each well at 450nm +/- 10nm with a microtiter plate reader. The results were read within 10 minutes.

Calculations

- 1) The average absorbance for each of the set standards, controls and samples was calculated.
- 2) After which a standard curve was plotted using a semi-logarithmic graph paper by plotting the mean absorbance obtained from each standard against its concentration with absorbance value on the vertical (Y) axis and concentration on the horizontal (X) axis.
- 3) With the mean absorbance values for each sample the corresponding concentration was determined from the standard curve.
- 4) The concentration of the samples was then directly read from the standard curve.

Reference Range: The reference range of serum Hcpidin in females is between 17-286 ng/ml. Different laboratories often use different units and “normal” may vary by population and the laboratory technique used.

Data Analysis

Collected data were entered into Microsoft Excel. Statistical analysis was then carried out using the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) software package (version 23.0), independent t-test and bivariate correlation. Statistical analysis outputs were presented using tables and graphs.

RESULTS

(Table 1) presents the demographic characteristics of the study participants, with 38 menorrhagic and 33 non-menorrhagic female students. The majority of participants in both groups were between 18-20 years old, with

63.2% in the menorrhagic group and 39.4% in the non-menorrhagic group. The highest proportion of students in the study were in their 500-level, with 39.5% in the menorrhagic group and 48.5% in the control group. Most participants reported beginning menstruation between ages 12-13 (52.6% for the menorrhagic group and 36.4% for the control group). Additionally, 100% of both groups were Nigerian, with Christianity being the predominant religion. Interestingly, Yoruba ethnicity had a higher representation in the menorrhagic group (57.9%) compared to the control group (30.3%) (**Table 1**).

(**Table 2**) shows a comparison of haematological indices between menorrhagic and non-menorrhagic groups. There was a significant difference in Total Iron Binding Capacity (TIBC) between the two groups ($p = 0.033$), where the menorrhagic group had a higher mean TIBC ($518.50 \pm 146.92 \mu\text{g/dl}$) than the control group ($443.08 \pm 144.34 \mu\text{g/dl}$). However, no significant differences were observed in other parameters like MCV, MCH, MCHC, PCV, RBC, and WBC between the groups (**Table 2**).

(**Figures 1**) to 6 show scatter plots exploring the relationships between TIBC and various haematological parameters. In all cases, there were no significant correlations observed between TIBC and MCV, MCH, MCHC, PCV, WBC, or RBC ($p > 0.05$). For example, Figure 1 shows that the correlation between MCV and TIBC was weak ($r = 0.0387$), and a similar trend was observed across the other parameters.

(**Table 3**) explores correlations between TIBC, haematological parameters, and menstrual characteristics. The results indicate no significant correlation between the duration of menses and TIBC ($r = 0.2277$, $p = 0.1692$), or the number of sanitary towel packs used and TIBC ($r = -0.1552$, $p = 0.3521$). However, a significant positive correlation was found between MCV and MCH ($r = 0.9354$, $p < 0.01$). Additionally, there was a significant inverse correlation between RBC and MCV ($r = -0.6919$, $p < 0.01$).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the study participants

Characteristics	Category	TEST (N = 38)	CONTROL (N = 33)
		Number (N) & Percentage (%)	Number (N) & Percentage (%)
Age range	18-20 Years	24 (63.2)	13 (39.4)
	21-22 Years	8 (21.1)	13 (39.4)
	23-25 Years	6 (15.8)	7 (21.2)
Study Level	100 Level	0 (0)	0 (0)
	200 Level	6 (15.8)	0 (0)

	300 Level	5 (13.2)	0 (0)
	400 Level	12 (31.6)	17 (51.5)
	500 Level	15 (39.5)	16 (48.5)
	600 Level	0 (0)	0 (0)
Age at first menstruation	<9 = 1	1 (2.6)	3 (9.1)
	9-11 = 2	6 (15.8)	12 (36.4)
	12-13= 3	20 (52.6)	12 (36.4)
	14-15= 4	9 (23.7)	3 (9.1)
	>15 = 5	2 (5.3)	3 (9.1)
Nationality	Nigerian	38 (100)	33 (100)
	Others	0 (0)	0 (0)
Religion	Christianity	36 (94.7)	33 (100)
	Muslim	2 (5.3)	0 (0)
	Others	0 (0)	0 (0)
Tribe	Igbo	8 (21.1)	9 (27.3)
	Hausa	0 (0)	0 (0)
	Yoruba	22 (57.9)	10 (30.3)
	Others	8 (21.1)	14 (42.4)
Height	< 1.20m	1 (2.6)	0 (0)
	1.20m-1.40m	0 (0)	2 (6.1)
	1.41m-1.60m	15 (39.5)	18 (54.5)
	1.61m- 1.80m	21 (55.3)	13 (39.4)
	>1.80m	1 (2.6)	0 (0)
Weight	< 40kg	0 (0)	0 (0)

	40kg-60kg	19 (50)	13 (39.4)
	61kg- 80kg	13 (34.2)	14 (42.4)
	81kg-100kg	4 (10.5)	6 (13.2)
	>100kg	2 (5.3)	0 (0)
BMI	< 18.5	2 (5.3)	0 (0)
	18.5-24.9	25 (65.8)	17 (51.5)
	25-29.9	5 (13.2)	9 (27.3)
	>30	6 (15.8)	7 (21.2)

Table 2: The mean± standard deviation of TIBC, RBC indices and WBC of menorrhagic female and controls

Parameter	Menorrhagic (N = 38)	Non-Menorrhagic (N = 33)	t-value	p- value
	Mean ± Std. Deviation	Mean ± Std. Deviation		
TIBC(μg/dl)	518.50 ± 146.92	443.08 ± 144.34	2.175	0.033*
MCV (fl)	85.44 ± 5.43	85.70 ± 7.77	-0.165	0.870
MCH (pg)	25.48 ± 1.49	25.70 ± 2.60	-0.425	0.673
MCHC (g/L)	297.84 ± 6.76	298.42 ± 6.86	-0.359	0.720
PCV (%)	35.88 ± 1.96	35.05 ± 3.06	1.342	0.185
WBC (x10⁹/L)	5.58 ± 1.47	6.17 ± 1.76	-1.529	0.131
RBC (x10¹²/L)	4.23 ± 0.33	4.10 ± 0.42	1.424	0.159

N = 71

Key: * => significant difference at p < 0.05

Figure 1: Graph (scatter plot) representing the relationship between MCV and TIBC
There was no significant positive correlation between the MCV and TIBC ($P > 0.05$).
With an $r = 0.0387$ showing no linear relationship between the variables

Figure 2: Graph (scatter plot) representing the relationship between MCH and TIBC

There was no significant positive correlation between the MCH and TIBC ($P > 0.05$).

With an $r = 0.0729$ showing no linear relationship between the variables

Figure 3: Graph (scatter plot) representing the relationship between MCHC and TIBC

There was no significant positive correlation between the MCHC and TIBC ($P > 0.05$).

With an $r = 0.2132$ showing no linear relationship between the variables

Figure 4: Graph (scatter plot) representing the relationship between PCV and TIBC

There was no significant positive correlation between the PCV and TIBC ($P > 0.05$).

With an $r = 0.2858$ showing no linear relationship between the variables

Figure 5: Graph (scatter plot) representing the relationship between WBC and TIBC

There was no significant positive correlation between the WBC and TIBC ($P > 0.05$).

With an $r = 0.1549$ showing no linear relationship between the variables

Figure 6: Graph (scatter plot) representing the relationship between RBC and TIBC

There was no significant positive correlation between the RBC and TIBC ($P > 0.05$).

With an $r = 0.1644$ showing no linear relationship between the variables

Table 3: Correlation of TIBC, haemoglobin and other parameters levels association with menorrhagia

Parameter		Duration of menses	No of sanitary towel packs per menstrual cycle	No of sanitary towel/day of menses	TIBC (µg/dl)	MCV (fl)	MCH (pg)	MCHC (g/L)	PCV (%)	WBC (x10 ⁹ /L)	RBC (x10 ¹² /L)
Duration of menses	Correlation Coefficient	1.0000	-.0756	-.0115	.2277	.0285	.0447	.0778	.2348	-.0564	.1126
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.6518	.9453	.1692	.8649	.7898	.6423	.1560	.7365	.5008
	N	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000
No of sanitary towel packs	Correlation Coefficient	-.0756	1.0000	.1308	-.1552	.0437	.0083	-.1779	.1585	-.2756	-.0007

per menstrual cycle	Sig. (2-tailed)	.6518	.	.4338	.3521	.7946	.9605	.2852	.3419	.0940	.9966
	N	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000
No of sanitary towel/day of menses	Correlation Coefficient	-.0115	.1308	1.0000	.0246	-.1206	-.0667	.0671	-.1944	-.1454	-.0427
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.9453	.4338	.	.8836	.4709	.6908	.6889	.2422	.3839	.7992
	N	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000
TIBC(µg/dl)	Correlation Coefficient	.2277	-.1552	.0246	1.0000	.0255	.0290	.0566	.2287	.1970	.1136
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.1692	.3521	.8836	.	.8794	.8627	.7358	.1672	.2357	.4969
	N	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000
MCV (fl)	Correlation Coefficient	.0285	.0437	-.1206	.0255	1.0000	.9354**	.0867	.1690	.1168	-.6919**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.8649	.7946	.4709	.8794	.	.0000	.6046	.3105	.4851	.0000
	N	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000
MCH (pg)	Correlation Coefficient	.0447	.0083	-.0667	.0290	.9354**	1.0000	.3661*	.1998	.0856	-.6153**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.7898	.9605	.6908	.8627	.0000	.	.0238	.2292	.6094	.0000
	N	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000
MCHC (g/L)	Correlation Coefficient	.0778	-.1779	.0671	.0566	.0867	.3661*	1.0000	.0976	-.0020	-.0425
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.6423	.2852	.6889	.7358	.6046	.0238	.	.5601	.9906	.8002
	N	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000
PCV (%)	Correlation Coefficient	.2348	.1585	-.1944	.2287	.1690	.1998	.0976	1.0000	.0124	.4833**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.1560	.3419	.2422	.1672	.3105	.2292	.5601	.	.9409	.0021
	N	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000
WBC (x10 ⁹ /L)	Correlation Coefficient	-.0564	-.2756	-.1454	.1970	.1168	.0856	-.0020	.0124	1.0000	-.0527
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.7365	.0940	.3839	.2357	.4851	.6094	.9906	.9409	.	.7535
	N	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000
RBC (x10 ¹² /L)	Correlation Coefficient	.1126	-.0007	-.0427	.1136	-.6919**	-.6153**	-.0425	.4833**	-.0527	1.0000

Sig. (2-tailed)	.5008	.9966	.7992	.4969	.0000	.0000	.8002	.0021	.7535	.
N	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000	38.0000

N = 38 ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

DISCUSSION

The study investigates the blood iron status of menorrhagic female students of Babcock University, comparing their hematological parameters with a non-menorrhagic control group. Menorrhagia, defined as excessive menstrual bleeding, can significantly affect iron metabolism, leading to iron deficiency anemia (IDA) in severe cases. The findings of this study align with those from previous research on the relationship between menorrhagia and altered iron levels but also provide new insights into the specific context of Nigerian university students.

The study group, composed of 38 menorrhagic and 33 non-menorrhagic students, exhibited distinct demographic characteristics. The majority of participants in the menorrhagic group were aged 18–20 years (63.2%), compared to only 39.4% in the control group, suggesting that younger individuals might be more prone to heavy menstrual bleeding. This contrasts with findings from a study by Fraser et al., which reported higher prevalence rates of menorrhagia in older women, indicating that age-related hormonal variations might play a different role in this population.^[7]

In terms of academic levels, both groups had higher representation from 400- and 500-level students, which may reflect the maturity of this age group or their greater awareness of health concerns related to menstruation. The age at first menstruation also showed noticeable differences, with the majority of menorrhagic participants (52.6%) reporting their first menstruation between the ages of 12–13 years, compared to a more evenly distributed onset in the control group. These findings correlate with a study by Munro et al., which suggested that early menarche could predispose individuals to irregular and heavy menstrual bleeding patterns.^[11]

Total Iron Binding Capacity (TIBC) was significantly higher in the menorrhagic group ($518.50 \pm 146.92 \mu\text{g/dL}$) compared to the control group ($443.08 \pm 144.34 \mu\text{g/dL}$) with a p-value of 0.033, indicating a significant difference. This suggests that the body's attempt to compensate for iron loss through increased iron-binding capacity might be more pronounced in individuals with menorrhagia, a finding that mirrors the results of a study by Liu et al., who found similar elevations in TIBC among women with excessive menstrual blood loss.^[12] Elevated TIBC is often a compensatory mechanism in response to depleted iron stores, reflecting increased production of transferrin, the protein responsible for iron transport.

However, there was no significant difference between the menorrhagic and non-menorrhagic groups in mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH), mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC), packed cell volume (PCV), white blood cell (WBC) count, and red blood cell (RBC) count. These parameters, although important indicators of overall hematological health, may not immediately reflect iron depletion until it becomes more severe. The lack of significant difference contrasts with studies like

those of Milman, where chronic menorrhagia was linked with reductions in MCV and MCH, indicating a shift toward microcytic, hypochromic anemia as iron deficiency worsens. ^[13]

The scatter plots and correlation analysis revealed no significant correlations between TIBC and the hematological indices, including MCV ($r = 0.0387$), MCH ($r = 0.0729$), MCHC ($r = 0.2132$), PCV ($r = 0.2858$), WBC ($r = 0.1549$), and RBC ($r = 0.1644$). These findings suggest that the relationship between iron-binding capacity and other hematological parameters in this population is complex and may be influenced by factors beyond simple iron depletion, such as individual variability in menstrual blood loss, diet, and compensatory hematopoiesis. This aligns with earlier work by Daru et al., which also found that hematological parameters might remain within normal ranges despite elevated TIBC in the early stages of iron depletion, emphasizing the importance of considering multiple diagnostic markers in clinical assessments of iron status. ^[14]

The significant elevation in TIBC, coupled with the absence of changes in RBC indices, suggests that many of the participants might be in the early stages of iron deficiency, where compensatory mechanisms are still preventing the development of overt anemia. This phenomenon was previously described by DeLoughery, who explained that iron deficiency may be present without anemia, especially in young women experiencing recurrent blood loss. ^[15] The compensatory increase in transferrin production in response to low iron stores can mask the early effects of iron loss on hemoglobin and RBC production.

Comparatively, a study by Sidhu et al. (2019) highlighted the importance of screening for iron deficiency in women with menorrhagia, even in the absence of anemia. ^[16] Their findings support the current study's observation that TIBC may be a more sensitive early marker of iron depletion than RBC indices, which typically reflect changes only after prolonged iron loss.

While the correlation between TIBC and the number of sanitary towel packs used per menstrual cycle was not significant ($r = -0.1552$), the trend observed in the data suggests that menstrual blood loss severity may influence iron-binding capacity. Although previous studies, such as that by Fraser et al., found stronger correlations between menstrual blood loss and iron status, the lack of significance in this study could be due to variations in individual reporting or other factors, such as diet or genetic predispositions, that were not controlled for in this sample. ^[7]

CONCLUSION

The study underscores the importance of assessing iron status in young women with menorrhagia, as many may be at risk of iron deficiency without showing classical signs of anemia. The elevated TIBC observed in the menorrhagic group suggests that these women may be experiencing early-stage iron depletion. Further longitudinal studies, with a larger sample size and additional markers of iron status such as serum ferritin and transferrin saturation, could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the progression of iron deficiency in this population. Additionally, interventions to improve dietary iron intake and reduce menstrual blood loss may be critical in preventing the progression of iron deficiency anemia.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- 1) **Routine Screening for Iron Deficiency:** It is recommended that regular screening for iron deficiency be implemented for female students, particularly those who report menorrhagic conditions. This can help in early detection and intervention to prevent severe iron deficiency anemia, which may lead to further health complications.
- 2) **Iron Supplementation Programs:** Establish targeted iron supplementation programs for women experiencing heavy menstrual bleeding. These programs should be designed to provide adequate iron intake either through diet or supplements to reduce the risk of iron depletion and anemia among this vulnerable group.
- 3) **Health Education and Awareness:** There is a need for increased health education on the importance of managing menstrual health and iron intake among young women. Awareness campaigns should be organized within the university to inform students about the risks associated with prolonged heavy menstrual bleeding and the importance of seeking medical advice.
- 4) **Further Research on Menorrhagia and Iron Status:** Additional longitudinal studies should be conducted to explore the long-term effects of menorrhagia on the blood iron levels and overall health of female students. Research should also explore other factors contributing to iron deficiency, such as dietary habits and genetic predisposition, to develop more comprehensive intervention strategies.
- 5) **Collaboration with Healthcare Providers:** Babcock University should collaborate with healthcare providers to establish specialized clinics or services that focus on menstrual health and anemia management. This collaboration can help in offering individualized care plans, including monitoring iron levels and providing appropriate medical care to students affected by menorrhagia.

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